

A Comparative Evaluation of Machine Learning Approaches for Fake News Classification in English-Language Online News Platforms

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Abstract

The proliferation of fake news across online English-language news platforms and social media threatens public trust and informed decision-making. This study focuses on detecting misinformation in English-language-based political and global news articles using a machine learning framework for binary classification (fake versus real). The research utilized a Kaggle dataset comprising 44,898 articles (52% fake, 48% real) from verified digital sources. Text preprocessing involved regular expressions for cleaning, NLTK for stopword removal and lemmatization, and TF-IDF vectorization with N-grams for feature extraction. Additional sentiment and topic features were generated via TextBlob and LabelEncoder, while SMOTE addressed class imbalance. Models evaluated included Logistic Regression (98.46% accuracy), Random Forest (99.85%), LinearSVC (99.31%), and Multinomial Naive Bayes (91.97%). Logistic Regression, optimized using GridSearchCV, was selected for its interpretability and computational efficiency, achieving comparable results to Random Forest. K-means clustering (silhouette score ~ 0.45) revealed intrinsic data structures supporting classification insights. The framework provides a reproducible, scalable approach to fake news detection applicable to online media monitoring systems. Limitations include English-only data and static news samples. Future work should integrate multilingual datasets and transformer-based models (e.g., BERT) for contextual depth and real-time detection. By defining a clear scope and refining interpretability, this study contributes a robust, domain-specific solution for misinformation detection.

Keywords: *Fake News, Machine Learning, Misinformation Detection, Natural Language Processing, Text Classification.*